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HISTORICAL AND IDENTITY CHARACTERISTICS OF KOREAN DIASPORA LITERATURE IN RUSSIA AS UNIFICATION AND MULTICULTURAL LITERATURE: FOCUSING ON THE SAKHALIN LITERATURE WORK “WHEN I BECOME THE SEA”

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ABSTRACT

Multicultural, multi-ethnic, and multilingual global cities have emerged due to the movement of modern global capital, labor, and technology, and free international migration through networks is giving rise to a new concept of diaspora. In a modern sense, diaspora can be defined as a concept encompassing international migration, refugees, migrant workers, ethnic community, cultural differences (multiculturalism), and identity, and in a classical sense, it has the meaning of ethnic dispersion and national separation originating from Jewish and Greek history. The purpose of this study is to examine the possibility of locality research as a unified and multicultural literature education based on the classical and modern concepts of diaspora in Russian Koryo Korean diaspora literature. At the same time, this study examines the differences in identity formation among Koryo-saram in Central Asia and Sakhalin Koreans, stemming from their respective historical backgrounds. It proposes that diaspora literature written in foreign languages, encompassing Korean identity and ethnicity, should be translated into Korean and included within the category of K-literature. Furthermore, through an analysis of Viktoriya Tsoi's contemporary diaspora literary work, *When I Become the Sea* (translated by this author), this research aims to demonstrate its potential function as a literary work for inter-Korean unification and as a text for multicultural education in the contemporary multicultural era.

KEYWORDS: Diaspora literature, Sakhalin Korean literature, Korean migration, modern literature, Choi Ok-sun/Choi Victoria.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Korean diaspora began with the migration of Koreans to the Russian Far East in the 1860s. The works of poets, novelists, and playwrights were published on the pages of the Korean newspaper 『Seonbong (先鋒)』, which was founded in Vladivostok on March 1, 1923. The literary pages of the “Seonbong Shinmun” featured the creative works of Cho Myung-hee (who was the editor-in-chief at the time), Han Byeong-cheol, Jo Gi-cheon, Yeon Seong-yong, Tae Jang-chun, and Kang Tae-su. In particular, the creative works of Cho Myung-hee, who had fled from Joseon, can be said to have been a practical example of creative activities by the Korean diaspora. The forced migration of the Koryo people in 1937 also made it difficult for Korean diaspora literature to continue its legacy. After the forced migration, there were no newspapers or magazines to publish, and the lack of education in Hangul and Korean, the national language, led to the loss of a linguistic basis for creative works.

Anatoly Kim, an eighty-year-old diaspora author who writes in Russian, is a representative example of a writer who crosses borders. There are very few writers of contemporary Russian Korean diaspora literature. Although within the same Russian territory, Sakhalin Korean diaspora literature has different historical characteristics.

The Korean diaspora book “When I Become the Sea” by Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon), a current permanent resident of Korea and third-generation on Sakhalin, contains the family history of four generations of Sakhalin compatriots—from 1830 to 2025, as well as the history of Korea (Joseon)–Japan–Russia by era: Koreans who were taken to Sakhalin coal mines for forced labor by the Japanese; grandparents who were drafted for forced labor and died longing for their homeland; the story of comfort women; the reason why Sakhalin Koreans were ruled again by the Soviet Union after Japan’s defeat in 1945, and why they remained stateless and then acquired Soviet citizenship; the first visit of South Koreans to Sakhalin right after the 1988 Olympics; the search for separated families between Sakhalin, South and North Korea; and the naturalization of Sakhalin Korean compatriots to Korea. These are all stories about family love, homeland, and the heartfelt desire

to return to one’s hometown—even if only through cremation and scattering one’s ashes at sea.

This work makes us realize the influence of our roots and our ancestors’ lives and experiences on our own personal lives as we were forcibly conscripted in Sakhalin, forced our Korean names to Japanese names during the Japanese colonial rule, and given Japanese names. We then acquired Soviet citizenship to change again as stateless people in Sakhalin and took on Russian names.

Since 2000, the South Korean government has promoted the permanent return of Koreans residing in Sakhalin. It passed the “Special Act on Support for Sakhalin Koreans”¹ in 2020². Furthermore, starting in 2025, the government is pursuing a project to support Sakhalin Koreans’ permanent return and settlement by expanding the scope of accompanying family members.³ Approximately 4,400 Sakhalin Koreans have permanently returned to South Korea and are living in the *Koryo* (Korean diaspora in the former Soviet Union) village in Ansan, Gyeonggi Province. They have moved from a life severed by forced conscription to Sakhalin to a new settlement and are living as multicultural citizens of South Korea. In other words, they are forming a new diaspora and multiculturalism, creating new cultural transformations.

The author believes that Sakhalin literature, overcoming borders, will serve as part of a multicultural literary education that will be able to find a common basis in the lives of Koreans who have been separated for a long time, and in the future—as part of a unifying literary education that will be able to find a common basis in the lives of Sakhalin Koreans who migrated from Russia to North and South Korea.

2. DIASPORA KOREAN LITERATURE AS A FORM OF UNIFICATION AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

The transformation of Korean literature from a peripheral or marginal literary movement to an integral part of the mainstream global literary discourse is evidenced by significant milestones such as the awarding of the Nobel Prize in 2024 to Han Kang, the first Asian woman recipient, and the receipt of the 2024 Tolstoy International Literary

¹ The purpose of this act is to provide relief for the damages suffered by Sakhalin Koreans who migrated to Sakhalin due to forced mobilization, etc., during the Japanese colonial period through diplomatic efforts with relevant countries, and to support the permanent return, settlement, and stable living of Sakhalin Koreans and their accompanying family members. <Amended January 16, 2024>

² World Korean News, “Sakhalin Koreans to Permanently Return with All Children,” January 16, 2024, worldkorean.net

³ The number of new applicants accompanied by family members in 2025 is projected to be 234 (Korean Embassy in Russia February Consular Newsletter).

Prize (Yasnaya Polyana Prize) in Russia by Korean-American writer Kim Joo-hye. These achievements emphasize Korean literature's increasing prominence and recognition on the global cultural stage. Korean literature, traditionally defined as "Koreans expressing Korean thoughts and emotions in the Korean language"⁴, is currently facing significant challenges in an era characterized by diversification and globalization.

Literature, a product of intellectual and conscious activity, functions as a mechanism to ensure equitable cultural and interpersonal interaction not only between individuals and ethnic groups but also between national entities and, by extension, the global community [Kwak Hyo-hwan 2011, 178]⁵. Within this paradigm, the Koryo-saram diaspora literature, formed in Russia and Central Asia, functions as a historically established community with a shared destiny. Its potential as such could be examined in the context of expanding and deepening the literary integration between North and South Korea that began in Russia and Central Asia. From the perspective of the literature in divided North and South Korea, as well as within the diaspora, it is essential to discuss and reach a consensus on how to view and embrace Korean literature produced both domestically and internationally. This includes Korean literature written in foreign languages and works that may arise in diverse cultural contexts. Addressing these aspects is crucial for the future globalization of Korean literature [Kwak Hyo-hwan, 2011: 179]⁶.

The work "When I Become the Sea" by Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon), a third-generation Korean born in Sakhalin, does not completely belong to the previously defined perspective on Korean literature. It is difficult to define as Russian literature a work written in Russian by a third-generation Korean that contains Korean culture, traditions, customs, and historical facts. It is important to discuss and consider whether literature created by the Korean diaspora – encompassing concepts of Korean nationality, identity, cultural customs, and history – should be categorized as Korean literature, particularly when it is written in a foreign language, as seen in the works of authors like Viktoriya Tsoi. In a scholarly context, individual identity is defined by how a person

attributes a sense of belonging to a specific group, such as a nation or ethnicity. The identity of migrants is characterized by their efforts to form new relationships with their country of settlement while simultaneously striving to maintain a connection with their country of origin. As a result, they live within a transnational social sphere that encompasses both nations, transforming their identities into transnational identities that traverse boundaries.⁷ This transnational identity is formed through continuous hybridization, blending cultural characteristics from their country of prior residence with those of their current host country.⁸ Consequently, Korean diaspora literature can be viewed as possessing a dual identity and a multicultural character.

3. IDENTITY OF THE KOREAN DIASPORA IN RUSSIA-CENTRAL ASIA, KOREANS IN SAKHALIN

Due to the migration policy of the Stalin era, most of the 560,000 Koreans in the Far East Primorsky Krai region were dispersed to Russia, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan. The term "Koreans in the Soviet Union", a new concept for a single ethnic group that was formed during the Soviet era, was used by second-generation Koreans born in the Russian Far East Primorsky Krai, mainly in the northern Hamgyeong Province, after the collapse of the Soviet Union, to refer to their ethnicity as "Koryo-Saram" and "Joseon Saram." However, today, due to the division of North and South Korea, descendants of Koreans who migrated to Russia (second to fifth generations) express their identity by saying, "We are neither South Koreans nor North Koreans. We are Koryo-saram." The first Korean newspaper, "Seonbong," established by Koreans who migrated to the Russian Far East, was renamed "Lenin Gichi," and later "Koryo Ilbo," after their forced migration to Central Asia. This change in naming is closely tied to the identity of the Koryo-saram.

On the other hand, the term "Sakhalin Korean," referring to Koreans living in the Soviet Union, is a Korean-focused term, and it is important to note the heterogeneity of its historical components. From 1939 until the liberation in 1945, for seven years, the Japanese colonial government used deception and

⁴ Cho, Yoon-je. *History of Korean Literature*. Tamgudang, 1986.

⁵ Kwak Hyo-hwan, "Trends and Directions of Globalization of Korean Literature Content Since 2000", *Comparative Korean Studies*, Vol. 19, No. 3, 2011, pp. 178.

⁶ Kwak Hyo-hwan, pp.179

⁷ Kang, Hoe-jin (2021). "Transnational Aspects in Overseas Korean Literature - Focusing on Poetry from Koryo-saram

Literature in Central Asia and Korean Chinese Literature." *Korean Literature and Arts*, Vol. 37, Soongsil University Institute of Korean Literature and Arts. pp. 2-4.

⁸ Lee, So-hee (2012). "Multicultural Society, Migration and Transnationalism." *Bogosa*. p. 21.

violence to resettle about 60,000 Koreans to Sakhalin and force them to work in the mines of Karafuto (the Japanese name for Southern Sakhalin). After Japan's defeat, about 47,000 Koreans remained on Sakhalin. Currently, the number of Koreans on Sakhalin (first to third generation) is 35,000. Sakhalin Koreans who remained in Sakhalin, which became Soviet territory after Japan's defeat, include those who studied in major cities such as Moscow, St. Petersburg, and Irkutsk and then stayed in the Soviet Union to work on contracts, or North Koreans who immigrated across the border and received residency permits. They are different from the Koryoins who were forcibly resettled in Central Asia; they speak Korean fluently. Thus, I believe that research and discussion are needed on whether diaspora literature should be divided between the Korean diaspora scattered across the same territory of the former Soviet Union, Sakhalin Koreans who identify themselves as Koreans, and Koryoins who claim to be neither Koreans nor people of the Joseon era, that is, whether Russia and Central Asia should be divided into Koryoins' literature, and the Sakhalin territory into the literature of Sakhalin Korean writers, or whether they should be considered as the same Koryoins' literature, and what criteria should be applied.

In the Far East of the Primorsky Krai, the literary page of the Korean newspaper "Seonbong" launched a new chapter in the diaspora literature of Koreans who migrated to the region. This legacy was further continued by the newspapers "Lenin Gichi" and "Koryo Ilbo." With the forced migration of Koryoins to Central Asia and the prohibition of education in their ethnic language, they were unable to receive education in Korean and thus lost the linguistic basis for their creations. Consequently, the literature of diaspora Koreans, known as Koryoins, did not receive adequate attention, nor did it develop or establish itself. Furthermore, during this period, all Koryoins who were interested in creative writing were extremely tense, fearing censorship of their works and violations of objectivity, which led to a decline in the literary quality of their works.

A representative example is the case of poet Kang Tae-soo, a disciple of Jo Myeong-hee, who was forcibly relocated to Kyzylorda, Kazakhstan, and who published a work titled "To a Plowing Girl," while longing for the peaceful days of Primorsky Krai. After that, he was branded an enemy of the people, arrested, and forced to endure 16 years of harsh labor. Works that expressed longing for the lost Joseon or the Primorsky Krai region were considered anti-state acts. In 2022, Professor Kim Pil-young translated into Korean the manuscript of author

Kang Tae-soo's account about his 16 years in the Soviet Union's Arkhangelsk concentration camp along with a manuscript of Tae-soo's poetry. The translated works were published under the title "In the Soviet Arkhangelsk Kulage; *В Советском Архангельском Кулаге.*"

It can be said that the social space and geographical meaning of the country of residence in which the works written in the local language reside, and the agony of wandering in multi-culture and multi-identity, are inherited and embraced in diaspora literature and Koryo-saram literature, which includes Korean culture and other local cultures in the country of residence.

Migration communities that were formed as a result of resettlement and adaptation from the Russian Far East to the Central Asian region, as well as the processes of cultural transformation, assimilation, integration, and coexistence that arose as a result of forced mobilization from the Korean Peninsula to Sakhalin Island, subsequently underwent division from the homeland due to political ideology. In the 21st century, these groups of Koreans migrated again to South Korea, which led to the formation of a new identity and a clash, with significant difficulties in adapting to the new socio-cultural environment. As a result of this process, phenomena of marginalization, intrapersonal and interpersonal conflicts, frustration, and maladaptation are observed. This determines the complex nature of their existence, characterized by a permanent personal identity crisis.

Establishing a direct connection between Koryo-saram diaspora literature—written in the politically fragmented context of the former Soviet Union—and modern Korean literature presents significant challenges. Despite these complexities, it is imperative to encourage the development of Eurasian diaspora literature by Koryo-saram descendants. Written in local languages, this emerging body of work should illuminate the lives of their ancestors who adapted to unfamiliar environments while preserving their Korean identity and cultural heritage.

This includes aspects such as: the social upheaval of the late Joseon Dynasty and the lives of migrants in the Russian Far East (Primorye); life and activities in this region, which served as a base for independence activists during the Japanese colonial period; life experiences following Koryo-saram forced migration to Central Asia; and the profound life changes after the collapse of the Soviet Union. Such literary endeavors will contribute to documenting and celebrating the resilience and

cultural continuity of the Korean diaspora.

The author of “When I Become the Sea,” Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon), a third-generation Sakhalin Korean, is currently a permanent returnee to Korea. Her work encapsulates a four-generation family history from 1830 to 2023. Following the dissolution of the former Soviet Union, Koryo-saram and ethnic Koreans have become geographically categorized, including those in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Sakhalin, and Ukraine. It is posited that by transcending the previous designation of “Koreans residing in the Soviet Union” and eliminating distinctions among Russian Central Asian Koryo-saram, Sakhalin Koreans, and Koreans from South Korea, a new direction for Eurasian diaspora literature and literature on the identity of Eurasian Koreans will emerge. This body of work, connecting the Korean Peninsula (North and South) with the Eurasian continent, is expected to serve as world literature, Korean literature, and unification literature, thereby also functioning as diaspora Korean literature. Consequently, Eurasian diaspora literature is anticipated to forge a crucial link between Koryo-saram literature and contemporary Korean literature, actualizing a 21st-century literary discourse that, as world literature, inherently reflects the global historical tragedies that impacted Korean literary heritage.

4. THEMATIC FOCUS OF SAKHALIN KOREAN WORKS

4.1. The History of Korean Migration to Sakhalin

The toponym “Sakhalin” was attributed to the island by the Mongols in the 13th century, meaning “rock entering the black river,” or, in the indigenous Ainu language, “island of birches.” Sakhalin is an island in the Sea of Okhotsk, east of Russia’s Primorsky Krai, located north of Japan’s Hokkaido. In Japanese, it is called “Karafuto” (樺太). Furthermore, the name “Sakhalin” originates from the Manchu toponym *Sahaliyan ula angga hada*, where *Sahaliyan* means “black” and *Ula* means “river,” collectively referring to the Amur River as “black river.” Thus, it denotes “the island opposite the Amur River.”⁹

Russians constitute the majority of Sakhalin’s population, accounting for nearly 80% of the total. Currently, the largest ethnic minority on Sakhalin is the Korean people, who make up 12% of the population. Following Japan’s defeat in the Pacific War in 1945, the Japanese repatriated only Japanese citizens and the indigenous Ainu people from the southern regions, abandoning those of Korean descent. Approximately 30,000 Koreans remain in Sakhalin Oblast, most residing in Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk.

Table 1: Overview of Russian and Japanese Territorial Control Over Sakhalin¹⁰

Sakhalin (the island across the Black River)	Russian/Japanese settlement and joint jurisdiction (1855–1875)
	Russian Sole Jurisdiction (1875–1905)
	Russo-Japanese partition (1905–1945): Russian territory north of 50 degrees north latitude (Sakhalin) / Japanese territory south of 50 degrees north latitude (Karafuto). Karafuto means “an island created by God at the mouth of a river.” It is derived from the shape of Sakhalin Island piled up at the mouth of the Amur River.
	Sole Russian jurisdiction (1945–present)

The migration of Koreans to Sakhalin Island commenced as early as the Imperial Russian era. Both Russia and Japan, in their efforts to develop this region, required substantial labor for coal mining, mineral extraction, oil development, fishing, and forestry on the island’s harsh terrain. This demand was so great that even exiled convicts were mobilized for labor. During this period, the Joseon Dynasty faced a precarious situation due to the weakening of its national foundation. Consequently, many farmers and manual laborers sought employment abroad,

with Sakhalin being one such destination. However, the majority of contemporary Sakhalin Koreans are descendants of those who were forcibly relocated and conscripted by Imperial Japan during the Japanese colonial period.

During the Pacific War, a theater of World War II, Japan’s need for coal production to sustain its war industries escalated. Consequently, Japan allocated personnel quotas at the county level to its then-colony, Joseon, and forcibly conscripted to Sakhalin one male head of household or son from each family.

⁹ Sakhalin, Namuwiki: <https://namu.wiki/w/%EC%82%AC%ED%95%A0%EB%A6%B0>

¹⁰ A brief examination of the territorial administration of Sakhalin by Russia and Japan reveals that in 1855, the Treaty of Shimoda (Japan’s name for the Russo-Japanese Treaty of Amity) was concluded, establishing Sakhalin as a joint administrative area for both nations. Subsequently, the 1875 Treaty of Saint Petersburg (Japan’s name for the Karafuto-Chishima Exchange Treaty) ceded

the entire Kuril Islands to Japan in exchange for Sakhalin becoming exclusively Russian territory. Following Russia’s defeat in the Russo-Japanese War of 1905, the Treaty of Portsmouth led to the reincorporation of northern Sakhalin into Russian territory, while southern Sakhalin was re-annexed by Japan. Japan subsequently established the Karafuto Civil Administration Office (樺太民政署) in this region.

By late 1944, the “National Conscription Order” led to the conscription of a large number of Joseon Koreans. Most of these forcibly conscripted individuals¹¹ originated from the Samnam region, specifically Chungcheong Province, Jeolla Province, and Gyeongsang Province.

According to Kim German [2013], for approximately seven years, from 1939 until just before liberation in 1945, the Japanese colonial regime forcibly relocated about 60,000 ethnic Koreans to Sakhalin through deception and violence, where they were subjected to forced labor in the Karafuto mines. After Japan’s defeat in 1945, it is reported that approximately 47,000 ethnic Koreans remained on Sakhalin. In 1947, Sakhalin Oblast was established as an independent entity, encompassing North Sakhalin, South Sakhalin, and the Kuril Islands. Japan’s abolition of the Karafuto government building (Karafuto-chō) in 1949 and its signing of the San Francisco Peace Treaty in 1952, relinquishing territorial claims over Southern Sakhalin, resulted in the entire island remaining part of Russian territory.¹²

Following the Soviet occupation of Sakhalin, while most Japanese residents were repatriated to the mainland, Joseon Koreans who had been conscripted to this territory—considered Japanese land during the colonial period—were treated as foreigners and negligently left stateless. They were also compelled to undergo socialist education and often faced disadvantages in their mining work due to a lack of knowledge regarding labor laws. Post-liberation, economically struggling North Korea dispatched approximately 50,000 contract laborers to Sakhalin, Primorsky Krai, and the Kamchatka Peninsula. The North Korean consulate encouraged stateless Koreans residing on Sakhalin to acquire North Korean citizenship. However, the Koreans residing on Sakhalin, none of whom originated from North Korea and most of whom had been conscripted from Gyeongsang and Jeolla Provinces, refused to acquire both Soviet and North Korean citizenship, intending to return to Korea. Their sole desire was repatriation to their homeland.¹³ While some did acquire Soviet citizenship during the 1960s and 1970s, the first generation, yearning for return to the Republic of

Korea, largely remained stateless and continued to endure difficult lives. These historical realities are thoroughly reflected in the second part of Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon)’s novel, “When I Become the Sea,” specifically in the “Karafuto” section, which vividly details the era and the history of migration.

Korean language education in Sakhalin resumed faster than in other Russian regions after the liberation from Japan in 1945. However, following directives from Soviet Central Committee General Secretary L.I. Brezhnev in 1964, ethnic education ceased, and ethnic Koreans were subsequently permitted only Russian language instruction. Nevertheless, after the 1988 Seoul Olympics, which occurred during a period of severed diplomatic ties with South Korea, Korean language education and teacher training resumed at Sakhalin State University in 1988. This reinstatement, predating the establishment of diplomatic relations with South Korea in 1990, signifies a crucial turning point, marking the genesis of a new revival in Korean studies and Korean language education [Kim Hye-ran, 2024:99].

After the Korean War in 1953, the two Koreas were divided, and Sakhalin Koreans were treated indifferently by the South Korean government, which had no contact with the Soviet Union during the Cold War. Many Sakhalin Koreans wanted to return to their hometown in Korea for economic reasons. In 2000, the South Korean government promoted the permanent repatriation of Koreans living in Sakhalin, and thousands of them returned permanently. The first-generation Sakhalin Koreans, born before 1945, who returned permanently, did so because they “wanted to be buried in their homeland.” However, they had to endure the sorrow of being separated from their families once again, as many left behind children in Sakhalin. Since the first seventy-seven people who returned to Sakhalin permanently in 1992, and since the enactment of the Special Act on Support for Sakhalin Compatriots in 2020, approximately 4,400 people have returned to Korea permanently. The Hometown Village Apartment Complex 1 in Ansan, Gyeonggi Province, was built by the Korea National Housing Corporation. The construction costs were supported by the Japanese

¹¹ It is important to note that Sakhalin Koreans differ from Koryo-saram, who voluntarily migrated to Manchuria and Soviet territories from the late Joseon Dynasty. While Koryo-saram in the Primorye region predominantly originated from northern areas such as Pyeongan and Hamgyong Provinces, Sakhalin Koreans primarily migrated from southern regions of the Korean Peninsula, including Gyeongsang, Jeolla, and Jeju Provinces, leading to distinct identity differences between the groups. Although voluntary migrants also existed on Sakhalin, they are

separately referred to as Sakhalin Koryo-saram. Victims of forced conscription from the southern Korean Peninsula and their descendants tend to identify themselves as Hanin (ethnic Koreans) rather than Koryo-saram.

¹² 『한국민족문화대백과사전』 “사할린 한인회”에서 발췌. Excerpt from “Sakhalin Korean Association” in the “Encyclopedia of Korean Culture.”

¹³ Excerpt from the Sakhalin Korean Society section of the *Encyclopedia of Korean National Culture*.

Red Cross for the first-generation Sakhalin Koreans who returned permanently. In response to demands for expanding the scope of permanent returnees, the revised Special Act on Support for Sakhalin Koreans was enacted, broadening eligibility from “one direct descendant” to “children.” This legislation became effective on July 17, 2024. Consequently, first-generation Sakhalin Korean parents and their children, as well as second-generation Sakhalin Korean siblings, can now repatriate and live together in Korea without experiencing the sorrow of separated families.¹⁴

4.2. Sakhalin Korean Work <When I Become the Sea 내가 바다가 될 때>, Motherland 조국

Korean diaspora literature, defined as Korean literature in major overseas regions such as the United States, Japan, China, and Russia, where Koreans write and engage in creative activities in Korean, raises various issues in the categorization of diaspora literature [Kim, Jong-hoe, p. 141]¹⁵ and Korean literature. These issues are based on bloodline, language, and national consciousness from the perspective of the era of globalization that transcends borders. Among them is also the linguistic problem of creation in Korean over generations. However, literature written based on national consciousness and the “national identity” of the Korean people can be said to be Korean literature. The author believes that Korean diaspora literature written in Russian (a foreign language), based on the identity of the Korean people, is important from the perspective of reproducing diaspora and local culture. Literary works translated from foreign languages into Korean should be included in the category of Korean literature from the perspective of cultural transformation as Korean diaspora literature created in a foreign language due to language barriers.

Especially in Central Asia and Russia, where communication has been cut off due to political and

historical circumstances, the cultural translation of Korean diaspora literature written in the local language can create understanding and sympathy between the two countries. In addition, cultural translation that informs about the Korean cultural heritage, traditions, and understanding of local cultures in Russia and Central Asia is believed to narrow the cultural gap between Korea and Russia. The world historical experiences and sympathy of modern and contemporary Koreans can allow Korean literature to occupy a special position in the world.

Korean diaspora literature writer Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon) introduces the cultural representation of the Korean locality in Sakhalin, Russia through her family history spanning four generations. She maintains Korean identity even in tough times, while introducing in detail Korean traditional culture and customs to Russian readers. The 57-year-old author, Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon), majored in economics rather than literature, and began writing short stories while working as a customs agent at the Sakhalin office. She revealed that her short story “The Road to Grandmother” was published in the Sakhalin Korean newspaper “Saegoryo Shinmun,” which led her to write a book about Sakhalin Koreans. This is a creative novel based on world history and dealing with the pain, suffering, and love of Koreans. Born in the USSR, Reya Kim grows up experiencing the Soviet Union’s collapse and Perestroika with her family. In the process, she learns about the history of Sakhalin Koreans and realizes that her life and the fate of her ancestors are inextricably linked. This novel won the Sakhalin Kuznetsov Literary Award in Russia and the Far East Arseniev Literary Award for long novels. The novel is composed of five parts, where each part connects the stories of a Korean family’s four generations, based on historical facts. It conveys the harmonious relationship between the thoughts, feelings, lifestyle, and long-standing interests of Sakhalin Koreans.

Table 2: Work Overview.

Title	<i>When I Become the Sea</i> (Russian Title); <i>Motherland</i> (Korean Title)
Author	Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon), 57 years old; Third-generation Sakhalin Korean (Permanent repatriate to Korea, residing in Incheon)
Genre	Historical Fiction (covering 1830–2023), narrating the story of four generations of migrant Koreans. Recipient of the Sakhalin Kuznetsov Literary Prize and the Primorsky Krai Far Eastern Arsenyev Literary Prize.
Setting	Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk (Russian name); Karafuto (Japanese name); Vladimirovka (Tsarist Russian penal colony)

¹⁴ Joogan Gippeun Sosik (Weekly Good News) (<http://www.igoodnews.or.kr>)

¹⁵ Kim, Jong-hoe (2015). *Korean Diaspora Literature*. Munhak-kwa Jiseongsa. p. 141.

Structure	Part 1: School	Part 2: Karafuto	Part 3: Youth	Part 4: Family	Part 5: Grandmothers
Time and Space	•1979, 1830: Soviet Union, Sakhalin Island, Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk	•1947, 1967: Karafuto	•1983, 1990: Soviet Union, Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk – Siberia	•1990: Perestroika	•2008: Sakhalin, Saint Petersburg, Ansan City (South Korea)
Table of Contents	•Vladimirovka •Pelmeni (Mandu) •Impressionists •Gypsies •Mathematics	•Decree/Order •Coal Mine •Evening •Way Home •Return/Repatriation •Mizuho •Defeat •Evening Guest •Three Shoemakers (a painting with three names) •Hairpin	•Aunt Miyoun •Exam •Konstantin •Cartoon •Reya’s Return •Encounter •Airplane	•Foreign Car •Important Matter •Frog •Casino •Vegetable Garden •Dishwasher •Bouquet •Funeral	•Trench Coat •Lost Mother •Stream •Boys •Companion •Alyona •Granddaughter •Anniversary
Key Terms		•Pacific War •Defeat •Comfort Women •Possession (by a spirit)	•Park No-hak •’88 Olympics	•Perestroika •Search for Separated Families	•Ansan City, South Korea •First-Generation Permanent Repatriates (Koreans) •First Birthday Celebration (Doljanchi), Doljabi (first birthday ritual) •Funeral •Sakhalin Korean Cremation Custom •First Ancestral Rite

With the onset of Perestroika, Reya’s life transforms. Her growing up unfolds against a backdrop of sweeping national changes. From childhood, Reya comes to understand why Confucianism values family more than anything else and realizes her inseparable connection to her ancestors. And much like the Koreans a century prior, she once again experiences the tragedy of a separated Sakhalin Korean family. She finally discovers why her grandparents wished to have their ashes scattered in the sea.

The first section, “School,” is set in 1979, in the city of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk on Sakhalin Island, part of the Soviet Union. Sakhalin’s name, given to it by the Mongols in the 13th century, means “rock entering the black river,” or, in the Ainu language, “Birch Island.” Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk, as Southern Sakhalin is called in Russian, was called Toyohara (豊原), meaning “rich hill,” during the Japanese period, and was the center of Japan’s Karafuto. Although Sakhalin¹⁶ became Russian territory in 1854, it was

used jointly by Russia and Japan, with Russia using it as a prison island. Like Siberia, Sakhalin’s early history was one of exile. People were needed to manage the exiles, and, in 1882, during the founding of the exile place, the settlement “Vladimirovka” (Владимировка) was created in honor of Vladimir, the overseer of the convicts.¹⁷

The 13-year-old ethnic Korean girl Reya Kim, who is residing in Vladimirovka, is an honor student attending a Soviet middle school. After school, Reya visits her 65-year-old maternal grandfather and 63-year-old maternal grandmother, who live in a detached house on the outskirts of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk, and helps them with household chores. While Reya is on the bus, returning home from her grandparents’ house, a Russian female passenger makes a derogatory remark about Koryo-saram (ethnic Koreans) to her. As a child, Reya took adult behavior for granted, but as she grew older, she began to wonder about the reasons behind such attitudes. Reya’s mother was reluctant to discuss the

¹⁶ The Russian writer Anton Chekhov, in his novel *Sakhalin Island*, written after his trip to Sakhalin in 1890, describes the island’s early pioneering phase when only about one hundred people lived there. He portrays it as a barren, uninhabited place, characterized as a penal colony. Chekhov also made the following remarks about Sakhalin: “Sakhalin is hell, a land of convicts and miserable people.” He further stated, “People say there is no climate here,

but there is bad weather, and they say this island is the harshest place in Russia.”

¹⁷ 유즈노사할린. 나무위키

<https://namu.wiki/w/%EC%9C%A0%EC%A6%88%EB%85%B8%EC%82%AC%ED%95%A0%EB%A6%B0%EC%8A%A4%ED%81%AC>

history of the ethnic Koreans (Koryo-saram) settling in Sakhalin, asking her daughter not to dwell on the past.

Based on my analysis, the protagonist's name, Reya, derives from the last two syllables of the word "Korea" (КОРЕЯ in Russian, KOREA in English) – a deliberate choice for the character's name. The novel effectively portrays the social discrimination and instability experienced by an ethnic Korean mother and her daughter, Reya Kim, as part of a minority group, through their daily lives in Vladimirovka, a locality that served as a penal colony for criminals and became a migration space. Later, the student Reya receives praise from her homeroom teacher for perfectly grasping the meaning of Anton Chekhov's journey, as described in his book "Sakhalin Island." Chekhov's post-travel observation, "Sakhalin is hell, a land of convicts and miserable people," and his further quote, "People say there is no climate here, but there is bad weather, and they say this island is the harshest place in Russia," can be seen as implying the difficulties faced by immigrants living in this region.

The second section, titled "Karafuto" (meaning Sakhalin in Japanese), recounts the experiences of ethnic Koreans living in the administrative district of Toyohara City (later Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk) in southern Japanese Sakhalin during the 1940s, alongside the story of Japan's defeat in World War II. Historically, following Japan's victory in the Russo-Japanese War of 1905, Japan occupied the portion of Sakhalin south of 50° North latitude. Despite the island's challenging climate, its rich deposits of oil and coal spurred the development of mining. Notably, to support its war efforts, Japan recruited or forcibly conscripted Korean laborers and transported them to the mines.

Upon the conclusion of World War II in August 1945, the Soviet Union (Russia) occupied the southern part of Sakhalin. At that time, approximately 368,000 Japanese nationals, including personnel from the 8th Division, and about 43,000 Koreans remained on the island. The Allied Command subsequently reached an agreement with the Soviet Union for the repatriation of Japanese residents from Sakhalin to Japan by December 1946. However, Koreans were excluded from this repatriation under the Potsdam Declaration, as they were not categorized as Japanese nationals. Consequently, the forcibly mobilized Koreans residing on Sakhalin became stateless under the Soviet regime. These Sakhalin Koreans were compelled to undergo socialist education and, due to their unfamiliarity with labor laws, not only faced disadvantages in their workplaces but also

experienced restrictions on their freedom of travel.

Seventeen-year-old Ok-sun lives in Toyohara City with her eighteen-year-old husband, Sang-il. The young couple arrived in Toyohara City on Sakhalin under the Japanese government's labor mobilization order. Like thousands of young Koreans, Sang-il endures a harsh life of labor, harboring the dream of returning to his homeland. The young couple welcomes the birth of their son, Nesang.

In August 1945, Sang-il learned that Japan had signed the instrument of surrender and that the Japanese were hastily leaving Sakhalin Island. Rumors spread that Russian soldiers would be cruel and would kill both Japanese and Koreans. Terrified, Ok-sun packs their belongings, and the family heads to Odomari Port to depart for Joseon (Korea). At the harbor, thousands of Joseon people flock to the departing ships, but only Japanese individuals are allowed on board for transport. After a few days, the young Kim couple realizes their efforts are futile and returns to Toyohara City. As the Soviet government takes over Toyohara City and civilian life on Sakhalin begins to recover, Sang-il returns to working in the mines. In accordance with inter-governmental agreements, Japanese citizens continued to be repatriated to their homeland, and the Joseon Koreans hoped for their turn. After several years, the Joseon Koreans gradually realized they were destined to remain on the island permanently. Engulfed in despair, Sang-il fell into dice gambling, losing all the rice he had farmed. The family endured a hungry winter.

Sang-il and Ok-sun lived out their lives on Sakhalin Island, working and raising their children, until their deaths. Ok-sun was able to meet her granddaughter Reya after her husband passed away, but his sudden death caused Ok-sun to lose her will to live, and life became hollow for her. Before they died, Sang-il and Ok-sun left a will for their son, Nesang, asking him to cremate their bodies and scatter their ashes over the sea. Sakhalin Koreans believed that this way at least small particles of their ashes would drift toward their distant homeland, Joseon (Korea). This section of the novel portrays the lives of the first generation of Koreans – Reya's grandmother, Ok-sun, and grandfather, Sang-il – in Karafuto, illustrating their suffering and pain, their efforts to maintain their Korean cultural heritage and identity as ethnic Koreans, and their yearning to return to their homeland.

The third section, themed "Youth," is set in 1983 in the Soviet Union, specifically in Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk and Siberia. Kim Reya graduates from school and departs for Novosibirsk to enroll in

university. There, she meets 17-year-old Konstantin, and they fall in love. After graduating from university, Reya returns to Sakhalin to tell her parents of her desire to marry Konstantin. This section effectively illustrates the struggles young ethnic Koreans in Russia face regarding identity preservation and interethnic marriage. Traditionally, Koreans have a custom of marrying within their own ethnic group. Reya experiences psychological unease and confusion about maintaining her identity amidst various conflicts with her family, her boyfriend of a different nationality, and herself, as she grapples with whether to break or uphold this tradition.

The fourth section, themed “Family,” is set against the backdrop of the Perestroika in 1990. In Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk a televised video conference between Korea and Sakhalin was held to facilitate the reunion of separated families among North, South Korea and Sakhalin. There, Reya meets 25-year-old Yevgeny Kim. The two young people marry and have two daughters. Yevgeny’s business of buying used Japanese cars prospers, and their home becomes filled with these vehicles. However, Reya does not love her husband, who becomes distant from her and regularly visits the casino. One day, after Yevgeny squanders all their family assets at the casino, Reya expels him from their home. Yevgeny (Zhenya) then goes to his grandmother’s house in Vladimirovka to help his elderly parents. He manages to repay all his debts within a year. Despite his parents’ pleas, Reya divorces Yevgeny (Zhenya).

This section illustrates the internal struggles of Reya, who, amidst dilemmas and conflicts about maintaining the Korean community within an immigrant family versus entering an international marriage, chooses an ethnic Korean husband. Yet, she faces family conflicts due to her husband squandering their assets at the casino.

The fifth section, titled “Grandmothers,” is set in Ansan City, South Korea, in 2008. This part delves into the experience of family separation that the first-generation Sakhalin Koreans and their direct descendants face once again, as only the first-generation are eligible for repatriation to South Korea. Japan formally acknowledged its obligations to the Sakhalin Koreans and initiated a repatriation program to return the elders, who had been mobilized half a century prior, to Korea. The grandmother, a first-generation Sakhalin Korean, departs for Ansan. Separated from her children and grandchildren, she develops dementia and is admitted to a nursing home. Reya’s parents decide to move to Korea to take care of the grandmother, leaving Reya alone on Sakhalin. Reya’s elder

daughter leaves to study in St. Petersburg, where she later falls in love with a young Russian man. On the very day Reya’s granddaughter is born to this young couple, the grandmother passes away in the nursing home. Reya travels to Korea to bid farewell to her grandmother. Following the Sakhalin Korean tradition, her grandmother’s cremated ashes are scattered at sea.

A year later, the entire Kim family gathers in Korea. They celebrate Reya’s granddaughter’s first birthday (*doljanchi*), and a few days later, they perform an ancestral memorial rite by the sea. The grandmother’s lifetime longing to return to her homeland, her *suguchosim* (a longing for one’s birthplace), finally sees her feet touch native soil. In accordance with Sakhalin Korean tradition, she is cremated, and her ashes are scattered at sea. This section beautifully illustrates the continuation of traditional Korean cultural elements such as first birthday celebrations, funerals, and weddings.

5. RESULT

Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon)’s long novel “When I Become the Sea” is written in a unique and beautiful style, showing Russian readers the world of the Korean ethnic community that was not well known, including family, women, traditions, language, and psychology. This novel, translated into Korean by the author, can be introduced not only to Korean readers but also to the Korean diaspora around the world, narrowing the long distance and broadening our understanding of the history of Goryeo-Koreans’ naturalizing in Korea, their identity, and the lives of the Korean diaspora. Viktoriya has opened the door to a unique Korean culture and ethnic style for many, especially to the unknown world of Sakhalin—a historical Russian and Japanese territory. Viktoriya Tsoi has expressed this Korean cultural world delicately and poetically, as well as honestly and vividly. She has also delicately connected the stories of four generations of a Korean family and tried to convey their thoughts and feelings, as well as the harmonious relationship between their lifestyle and long-standing customs.

In this novel, a major part of Korean diaspora literature and locality studies, you can hear the characters’ voices, smell the food, and even feel the way a woman places her teacup. Viktoriya Tsoi’s novel contains the sounds, smells, plants, colors, household items, habits, and superstitions of various eras that transcend time. The story of a Korean family living away from their home and roots is particularly poignant. Their pain and suffering, along with their desire to preserve their traditions and identity,

resonate with readers from all backgrounds. This is one of the most significant roles of the novel. It conveys wise thoughts that help people understand each other and overcome challenging times together by breaking stereotypes across geographical, cultural, and temporal boundaries.

Korean Koryo-saram literature, given its historical context, often faced censorship during its creation, which restricted the free expression of thought. This often led to a decline in artistic quality, resulting in less attention from a literary perspective. According to an interview with Professor Lee Dong-soon in *Nongaeg* magazine¹⁸, writers had to be cautious when using words like “homeland” or “motherland.” These terms had to be preceded by “Soviet.” Without this prefix, the expression could be misunderstood as referring to either South or North Korea. Furthermore, the term “forced migration” was, and still is, an extreme taboo in Koryo-saram media in Russia and Central Asia.

The title of Viktoriya Tsoi (Choi Ok-soon)’s novel is “When I Become the Sea” in Russian, while the title of the novel in Korean below is “Motherland.” This suggests that diaspora literature in which thoughts can be freely expressed during the creative process is possible. Although Viktoriya Tsoi was born as a third-generation Korean in the Soviet Union, this is a transnational literature that expresses the identity of Koreans as immigrants, as well as the wandering and agony of their family history in the social and geographical space of my grandparents and my own history. This work is not simply a spatial story of the former Soviet Union but a novel that connects the

past and present of the lives of their descendants from 1840 to the present, 2025, and thus, it is a work that creates a link in the disconnection, and its significance is great. Diaspora literary works that contain Korean history, society, culture, and identity, written in the local language, because their authors do not know Korean, should be translated into Korean to expand the scope of thinking about and discussing that literature. In addition, diaspora works translated into Korean should be included in the category of Korean literature, or K-literature, as works with a world-historical background as their subject. I believe that this will raise awareness of the Koryo people and Sakhalin compatriots who naturalized back to Korea as Koreans and motivate descendants to actively participate in creative activities about the spatial meaning, identity, wandering, and agony of their ancestors and their diaspora lives.

I would like to propose that we expand Korean content into borderless K-Korean literature beyond the confines of Koryo-saram literature. This can become a source of a new Korean Wave and open up the possibility for a new genre. In a borderless digital environment, Koryo-saram literature, K-Korean literature, as transnationalism with transnational, supranational, and unified national meanings, should move forward as “K-Korean literature as world literature, diaspora, multicultural literature, and Eurasian literature,” and there should be continuous efforts and discussions to solidify its position.

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